

Releasing everyone from prisons or Donald Trump turns himself over to North Korea

Is everybody really going to let this piece of shit administration politicians and anybody that wants to go with Donald Trump ruin America?

When Donald Trump didn't put up a wall that should have been a red flag but when he went to go plant listening devices and murdered those innocent people is when he became a criminal.

So you can either turn yourself into North Korea or everybody that's in prisons in jail needs to be released because if you can get away with crime so can everybody else and your crime was a war crime justified or not you people are just as guilty if you're going to back up murder what does the Trump administration have against Koreans or Asian people? No one has the brains or the balls to stand up for what's right besides me?

None of these people in power deserve to be in power as a matter of fact when you killed those people with lives, Mr. Trumpz that was when you forfeited your right to be the president at all. Why keep this guy around that does nothing but divide along with the politicians that aren't any better.

You all are all pieces of shit. The only way I see me keeping any of you around is to overthrow the administration, send your ass to North Korea Mr. Trump and that will be the first part of unification of the world which the whole Trump administration could have already done this themselves that's how much they care about you or your safety.

All you politicians and administration that can't seem to understand the concept of unification because you're too busy arguing trying to make money off of us people. If I had a say you all would be getting a taste of your own medicine by working for us, as we overthrow you all even the police that think that they are all high and mighty, we would be releasing people from prisons and jails under my authority.

If you can get away with murder and crime well so can everybody else. If I had A say we would make a Kingdom of America called The United States.

